

Data-driven solutions for asset maintenance

Data-driven solutions for railway asset maintenance are extremely relevant for:

- **monitoring** of assets
- efficient **scheduling** of maintenance interventions

Machine learning techniques can be used to support:

- the **prediction of asset failures**
- the **prescription of proactive maintenance activities**
- **optimisation of maintenance planning** considering different constraints

Challenges for integration in Intelligent Asset Management Systems

Reuse

The **reuse of digital artifacts** that can possibly support different maintenance scenarios

Examples:

- **Reuse** prediction component/model by different companies relying on assets from the **same vendor**
- **Reuse** component for maintenance planning optimisation by heterogeneous maintenance teams

Reproduce

The possibility for different actors to store and access obtained results and **information for reproducibility**

Examples:

- define repeatable procedures for **what-if analysis** over predictions
- define repeatable processes for the **optimisation** of maintenance plans

Trust

A mechanisms for the **auditing of the operations performed** by different users and systems

Examples:

- in **case of failures** of the railway network due to maintenance issues determine users and software components involved in the analysis of data related to the damaged assets

IAMS Integration Support Framework

Describing and tracking each digital artifact individually is not enough to foster reproducibility and trustability. We introduce:

- **Intelligent Maintenance Package:** describes a maintenance scenario that leverages different digital artifacts and can be executed in an integrated runtime environment
- **Intelligent Maintenance Session:** describes the information about operations made by a user in the interaction with digital artifacts composing an Intelligent Maintenance Package

Session ID	Time	Components	Inputs	Outputs
Session-1c2053fa-7aa0-4ace-b8ba-173819abe469	March 1, 2023 at 1:24:13 PM GMT+1			
Session-0199a30a-5247-4e15-9e0d-f70ce3ea7cb4	February 27, 2023 at 1:18:58 PM GMT+1			
Session-7006bd22-1516-4055-af3f-6beae28519d2	February 27, 2023 at 9:00:41 AM GMT+1			
Session-6b823c77-30b6-4e6b-b501-2c90ec0169cc	February 16, 2023 at 3:51:32 PM GMT+1			
Type	Time	Components	Inputs	Outputs
predict	February 16, 2023 at 4:51:32 PM GMT+1	Software component/ACME Prediction	Machine learning model/PEM Machine learning model/RLM Machine learning model/RTM	
predict	February 16, 2023 at 4:51:38 PM GMT+1	Software component/ACME Prediction	Machine learning model/PEM Machine learning model/RLM Machine learning model/RTM	
train	February 16, 2023 at 4:52:26 PM GMT+1	Software component/ACME Model Training	Dataset/ACME Maintenance data Dataset/ACME Weather data Dataset/VM/VPL D data Dataset/TC system boards parameters Dataset/Central Control System (CCS) logs Dataset/ACME Bin files	Machine learning model/PEM

Watch the video!
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